

Project Acronym:	NOVETROL
Grant Agreement number:	101192615 (HORIZON-CL5-2024-D2-01)
Project Full Title:	Novel current control for climate neutral energy infrastructure

DELIVERABLE

D3.2 – EMR Component Report

Dissemination level:	PU -Public
Type of deliverable:	R -Report
Contractual date of delivery:	30 January 2026
Deliverable leader:	SAL
Status - version, date:	Final – v1.0, 2026-01-28
Keywords:	Current limiter; design; fabrication; modelling; magnetoresistance

Deliverable leader:	SAL
Contributors:	Luiz Enger (SAL), Jérémy Létang (SAL), Nikolaos Fotias (EAT)
Reviewers:	UPB, ICPE-ACTEL
Approved by:	UPB

Document History			
Version	Date	Contributor(s)	Description
0.1	23/12/2025	Luiz Enger	Initial ToC and first draft
0.2	19/01/2026	Luiz Enger	Updated ToC and first draft
0.3	27/01/2026	Luiz Enger	Update after review
1.0	28/01/2026	Luiz Enger, Jérémy Létang, Nikolaos Fotias	Final version for submission

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
Table of Figures	3
Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Modelling the magnetoresistive component	6
2.1. Choosing the appropriate material and introduction to extraordinary magnetoresistance	6
2.2. Current limiter vs sensing applications	8
2.3. Development of an analytical model	9
3. Fabrication of the component	11
3.1. Wafer acquisition	11
3.2. Sample design and fabrication	11
4. Characterization of the component	12
5. Conclusions	19
References	20

Table of Figures

Figure 1: The colours represent the electric potential, and the arrows show the current direction. a) At zero magnetic field, metallic inclusion acts as a bypass and the measured voltage difference is negligible. b) With magnetic field perpendicular to the plane, current is deviated and remains in the semiconductor, giving rise to higher voltage difference.....	7
Figure 2: Signal variation from commercial InSb device, performing voltage measurements in different configurations.....	9
Figure 3: Solid line (red) indicates initial current path, and dashed line indicates the deviated path. Magnetic field is orthogonal to L and W and parallel to t, not shown here.	9
Figure 4: Solid lines indicate current path in each design. The width W and direction of current deviation are perpendicular to the visible plane, and external magnetic field is applied parallel to the thickness t.....	10
Figure 5: InSb wafer with patterned electrodes for test samples in the planar design.....	12
Figure 6: Cleaved dies of InSb samples in the planar design, ready to be integrated in PCBs.12	
Figure 7: Impact when electrodes are not equipotential. In i) only four wire bonds are present, whereas the whole length of the electrodes is covered with wires in ii), reaching a higher MR. The table indicates the resistance values R_0 and R_1 at 0 T and 1 T fields respectively, and the corresponding MR.	13

Figure 8: Custom magnetic field generator with a test sample placed inside the airgap.14

Figure 9: PCB design as drawn in KiCad suite. As a double-layer PCB, the top copper is shown in red and the bottom copper in blue.....15

Figure 10: Sample used for wire bonding test. Several Au wires of 25 μm diameter were used to make electrical connection between sample electrodes and PCB pads.16

Figure 11: Top view of PCB after sample integration and soldering of banana sockets.17

Figure 12: Sourcemeter supplying 10 mA fixed current and measuring voltage with independent terminals. Value of 0.79 mV at zero field.17

Figure 13: Measured voltage increases to 10.06 mV at 1 T field, obtained from the custom field generator.18

Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Title
AC	Alternating current
AMR	Anisotropic magnetoresistance
DC	Direct current
EMR	Extraordinary magnetoresistance
FEM	Finite-Element Modelling
GMR	Giant magnetoresistance
HEMT	High-electron-mobility transistor
MR	Magnetoresistance / magnetoresistive
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
TMR	Tunneling magnetoresistance

1. Introduction

This document, D3.2 – EMR Component Report, defines the design, fabrication, characterization and testing of the magnetoresistive (MR) component.

The document discusses:

- The choice of material for the MR component in the context of NOVETROL project
- The differences between developing a MR device for sensing applications based on the effect commonly labelled as extraordinary magnetoresistance (EMR) and developing a MR device for current limiting applications
- The development of analytical expressions to estimate the resistance of the MR element with and without the presence of a magnetic field as a function of geometry and relevant material properties
- The modelling and simulation of such devices via Finite Element Modelling (FEM) approach using commercial software
- The fabrication procedure followed in clean room environment to obtain the desired components as designed
- The characterization steps used in the Magnetics Laboratory to obtain experimental data from the samples, and understand their electrical and magnetic behaviour

From requirements defined previously in D2.1 and D3.1, a set of resistance values at zero and high magnetic fields for each use case can be obtained, which will guide the design of the MR elements.

2. Modelling the magnetoresistive component

2.1. Choosing the appropriate material and introduction to extraordinary magnetoresistance

For the current limiter application in the context of NOVETROL, a component that can switch from a low electrical resistance state to a high electrical resistance state is required. Positive thermal coefficient thermistors are a very well-known and widely used solution, but the time scales of thermal effects are longer than the requirements found in NOVETROL use-cases. Another possibility is to exploit the MR effect: the change of the electrical resistance of an element based on the presence of an external magnetic flux density B^1 . As soon as the magnetic field is present, the change in resistance is observed. It is a much faster effect than its temperature-based counterpart.

The MR effect has widespread usage in magnetic field sensing applications, with proven technologies such as anisotropic MR (AMR), giant MR (GMR), and tunnelling MR (GMR) that are extensively integrated into a plethora of devices used by millions of people every day. Less known in the xMR family is the extraordinary MR (EMR). First presented by Solin [1], signal variations that are orders of magnitude higher than previously shown by AMR, GMR and TMR were obtained when a semiconductor with high mobility of charge carriers μ has a metallic inclusion into it. Since then, studies have been conducted on the impact of material choice, device geometry, contact resistance and other influences, many of them based on

¹ the terms magnetic flux density and magnetic field will be used interchangeably during this document, as the difference between both terms is negligible in this context.

investigations using Finite Element Modelling (FEM) simulations. Many of such investigations are collected in [2].

As a 4-terminal device, two ports are used as input and output for the electric current path, while two other ports are used to measure a voltage difference. At zero magnetic field, the electric current flows through the metallic inclusion due to lower resistivity, bypassing the semiconductor body. The current that flows near the voltage measurement ports is negligible, thus the voltage difference between the two voltage measurement terminals is practically zero. At increasing magnetic field intensity, the current lines strongly deviate inside the semiconductor due to the strong Lorentz force². In this case, more and more current flows in the semiconductor body with the increase of the magnetic field. Figure 1 shows the FEM simulation results for a InSb disk with metallic inclusion in its center. Two terminals are for the current injection path ($I+$ and $I-$) and two terminals are for voltage measurement ($V+$ and $V-$).

Figure 1: The colours represent the electric potential, and the arrows show the current direction. a) At zero magnetic field, metallic inclusion acts as a bypass and the measured voltage difference is negligible. b) With magnetic field perpendicular to the plane, current is deviated and remains in the semiconductor, giving rise to higher voltage difference.

The segment between the two voltage measurement ports can be seen as an internal resistor, and now when the current flows, a voltage difference arises. This voltage can be enhanced by the Hall voltage that surges from the charge accumulation around the edges of the semiconductor and the metallic inclusion [3]. When writing the difference between the voltage measured in the presence of an external field and the near-zero voltage difference measured at zero field, the signal variation (voltage difference with field minus voltage difference without field) is of several orders of magnitude.

Among materials with very high mobility of charge carriers, one can find Indium Antimonide (InSb) and graphene encapsulated in hexagonal boron nitride (hBN). Both devices have been studied for the development of magnetic field sensors based on EMR with very high sensitivity. As the underlying effect is the same as in Hall devices (deviation of current with

² Lorentz force due to high charge carrier mobility μ ; $F \propto (\mu \cdot E) \times B$

Lorentz force), one can also find commercially available Hall sensors based on InSb [4]. Another type of material that presents very high mobility is two-dimensional electron gas, formed in heterostructures made of semiconductors with mismatching energy bands, and used in high-electron-mobility transistors (HEMTs) [5]. Among the selected materials, only InSb presents itself as a suitable choice in NOVETROL for designing a fully passive current limiter³.

2.2. Current limiter vs sensing applications

Before diving into the modelling process of the proposed solution, it is important to distinguish the differences between a 4-terminal sensing device and the 2-terminal MR current limiter. The magnetoresistance ratio of 2-terminal devices is defined as the relative change in resistance, expressed as:

$$MR = \frac{R_1 - R_0}{R_0} \quad (1)$$

Where R_0 is the resistance in ohms at zero magnetic field and R_1 is the resistance in the presence of an external magnetic field. It is also common to present this value in percentage. This relation holds when the electrical current flows through the same terminals as the ones used to measure the voltage, which is the case of the proposed current limiter.

As mentioned before, the high values of signal variation found in 4-terminal EMR devices comes from the variation of the voltage difference between two terminals that are independent of the input and output current terminals, much like a Hall effect device. In this sense, one can write the expression for EMR as:

$$EMR = \frac{\Delta V_1 - \Delta V_0}{\Delta V_0} \quad (2)$$

Where ΔV_0 and ΔV_1 are the voltage differences measured at zero field and in the presence of an external magnetic field, respectively. Whereas the expressions have the same form, their dependencies and limitations are completely different. Because ΔV_0 is extremely low, EMR variations can be orders of magnitude higher than MR variations, even for the same material and device geometry.

Although it is a Hall device, Figure 2 shows this distinction for HW101, a commercial sensor made of InSb by Asahi Kasei Microdevices [6]. The signal variation when using all four terminals of the device is more than two orders of magnitude higher than when using only two terminals.

³ High current density values would destroy the delicate graphene, while HEMTs require active control.

Figure 2: Signal variation from commercial InSb device, performing voltage measurements in different configurations.

2.3. Development of an analytical model

The magnetoresistance effect found in large mobility semiconductors strongly depends on the geometry of the device. Obtaining an analytical expression for MR based on the geometry parameters is a key objective in understanding how the performance of the device can be enhanced and what its limitations are. Figure 3 shows a simplified schematic of the MR current limiter component, consisting of a semiconductor main body and two metal electrodes for the input and output of the electric current.

Figure 3: Solid line (red) indicates initial current path, and dashed line indicates the deviated path. Magnetic field is orthogonal to L and W and parallel to the thickness t , not shown here.

At zero magnetic field, the electric current flows from the input to the output electrodes separated by a distance L , with a corresponding resistivity ρ_0 . In the presence of external magnetic field, the current path gets deviated to an effective path L' with a field dependent resistivity ρ_{eff} . The deviation distance of the current lines is represented by W , and the semiconductor has a thickness t . As a first approach, charge accumulation at the edges is ignored, and the device behaves like a Corbino disk [7] in which all current lines are deviated as much as possible. This is equivalent to considering an infinitely long semiconductor body. By rewriting the conductivity tensor as a function of magnetic field and comparing the equivalent resistance along L and along L' , the maximum MR that can be achieved in a 2-terminal device is $MR = \mu^2 B^2$. As an example, considering InSb with $\mu = 7 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ under a field of $B = 1 \text{ T}$, the maximum achievable MR is of 4900 %. The fabrication and integration of InSb samples as current limiters in Corbino disk geometry are not feasible,

therefore it was decided to maintain the design with edge contacts as shown in Figure 3. In reality, the effect of geometry and charge accumulation at the edges cannot be completely ignored. Through a phenomenological approach with the support of FEM simulations, the expression for maximum MR was modified to:

$$MR = \frac{\mu^2 B^2}{1 + \frac{\mu |B| L}{W}} \quad (3)$$

In this geometry where the sides of the semiconductor are fully covered by metal, the thickness t of the semiconductor has no effect on the resistance variation, only on the resistance absolute values. A correction must be done when the metal electrodes make an electrical connection only from the top surface of the semiconductor, as shown in Figure 4. For convenience, the first and second design are named *sandwich* and *planar*, respectively.

Figure 4: Solid lines indicate current path in each design. The width W and direction of current deviation are perpendicular to the visible plane, and external magnetic field is applied parallel to the thickness t .

Due to this difference in current injection, the MR ratio for the planar design is generally lower than for the sandwich design for the same electrode width W and distance between electrodes L . The MR ratio in the sandwich design is approached by the planar one when the L/t ratio is increased, which can be done either by reducing the InSb thickness or designing samples with longer L . Effectively, this makes the region of InSb not covered by metal the dominating contribution, much like in the sandwich design.

2.4. Finite Element Modelling Environment

The COMSOL Multiphysics® software was chosen to perform FEM simulations since it allows for the implementation of user-defined equations, which was crucial to simulate the desired effect correctly and to solve for the dependence of the conductivity on the magnetic field. It was assumed that the electron mobility in InSb is $7 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{V}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and isotropic when at zero magnetic field, whereas the field direction affects only components that are not parallel to it.

Expressions for the dependence of electron mobility and charge carrier concentration on temperature were also included. Such relations can be obtained from [8] and [9]. This is crucial to understand how the self-heating from Joule effect will impact the performance of the MR component, as we intend to pass higher current levels through the component compared to the current levels used in sensing applications. While the carrier concentration rises with temperature, the electron mobility decreases. Due to a higher increase in carrier concentration than a decrease in mobility for the same increase in temperature, this results

in a higher conductivity, which reduces the absolute electric resistance. And as the MR is a function of mobility squared, the resistance variation also suffers strongly. Thus, it is of most importance to find ways to obtain a passive cooling solution for the device, and to keep its temperature near ambient values even when several amperes are flowing through it.

3. Fabrication of the component

3.1. Wafer acquisition

For the fabrication of samples, commercially available n-type InSb wafers with 50 mm diameter (2" size) and 600 μm thickness were purchased. It was requested that wafers should present the highest mobility of charge carrier μ as possible, at room temperature.

3.2. Sample design and fabrication

The fabrication of the samples followed standard microfabrication techniques, such as photoresist coating, photolithography exposure, photoresist development, metal layer deposition and lift-off. All steps were performed inside the ISO 5 cleanroom at Silicon Austria Labs GmbH in Villach. The Graphic Data System (GDS) file required for the photolithography step was prepared with the open-source software Klayout [10]

The photoresist AZ[®] nLOF 2020 from MicroChemicals was used to cover the wafer, following an internally developed recipe. Photolithography exposure was conducted with a direct laser writing equipment, which allows to test different designs without the need to order physical photolithography masks. After development with AZ[®] 726 MIF Developer and a short low O₂-content plasma, the wafers were loaded into an electron-beam evaporation chamber. A dual layer of Ti (30 nm, for adhesion improvement) and Au (300 nm) was deposited to prepare the electrodes. Finally, wafers were soaked overnight in TechniStrip[®] Micro D350 and cleaned with deionized water. To obtain the dies, the wafers were manually cleaved after marking with a diamond pen. A company capable of performing professional grinding and dicing of this material was already identified. A full 50 mm wafer with patterned electrodes is shown in Figure 5, and Figure 6 shows samples after cleaving.

Figure 5: InSb wafer with patterned electrodes for test samples in the planar design.

Figure 6: Cleaved dies of InSb samples in the planar design, ready to be integrated in PCBs.

4. Characterization of the component

4.1. Integration in Printed Circuit Board

To be able to perform the electrical measurements, first the sample under study must be integrated onto a Printed Circuit Board (PCB). One method to easily integrate samples with varying designs in PCBs is with wire bonding. Whereas thicker wires such as 100 μm diameter wires made of Aluminium would be more suited for this application due to lower DC resistance and better current carrying capacity, the necessary minimum ultrasonic energy to establish a

bond between wire and gold pad is too high for the brittle InSb. In the initial tests, the InSb material was chipped below the contact area, resulting in small crater-like breakouts. Therefore, thinner Au wires with 25 μm diameter were used. As a rough approximation, 1 mm length of a 25 μm Au wire has 50 m Ω DC resistance. To reduce the added DC resistance from the Au wires, it is necessary to include as many of them as possible.

Another reason to add as many wire bonds as possible is the following: indium antimonide has a considerably higher conductivity compared to silicon and other semiconductors. If the electrical contact from the PCB pads to the deposited electrodes is not done properly, the input or output electrode might not be completely equipotential. This hinders the achievable MR performance, since this effect can be considered as having a smaller effective W . Figure 7 shows the top-view of a FEM comparison in a planar sample, when only a few wire bonds are used in the middle versus wire bonding covering the whole electrode area.

Figure 7: Impact when electrodes are not equipotential. In i) only four wire bonds are present, whereas the whole length of the electrodes is covered with wires in ii), reaching a higher MR. The table indicates the resistance values R_0 and R_1 at 0 T and 1 T fields respectively, and the corresponding MR.

Although bonding with wires is straightforward and quick, a better option for integration of the InSb samples in the PCB is the use of custom-made copper clips. Such clips cover entirely the metal electrodes on the sample, with a DC resistance no higher than 0.1 m Ω when copper sheets of 0.35 mm thickness are used. To attach the clips to the PCB and to the sample, standard soldering process with lead-free solder paste can be used, with a solder reflow oven. This also allows the integration of several units at once. Besides lower DC resistance and achieving equipotential electrodes, the copper clips also help with heat extraction from the InSb component thanks to its higher thermal conductivity.

4.2. Improving thermal management

While the topside of the sample is used for electrical contact, the bottom side can be used to dissipate the thermal energy away. The InSb sample can be placed on top of an exposed metal zone in the PCB, which is shorted to a large floating copper plane. Still, the sample must be electrically insulated from this plane. So far, two options were identified to achieve electrical insulation and good thermal conductivity between the InSb sample and the heat sinking plane. One option is thermally conductive insulators pads such as TCIN series from MTC[®] [11], with the highest possible conductivity of 7 W \cdot m⁻¹ \cdot K⁻¹ and lowest possible thickness of 0.5 mm. A second option is a thermally conductive and electrically insulating epoxy such as Duralco[™] 4700 from Cotronics [12]. Although its conductivity is more than three times lower

than that of the pad, a layer that is more than one order of magnitude thinner can be obtained with the glue. This results in a smaller thermal resistance.

4.3. Measurement setup

To perform the electrical measurements, the Keithley 2460 Sourcemeter was used. With two ports for current injection and other two independent ports for voltage measurement, such equipment can be used to measure low DC resistance values by avoiding contributions from the cables. This is known as a 4-point measurement. To correctly measure the resistance variation of the 2-terminal current limiter in a 4-point setup, each pad of the PCB that is contacted to the sample has two outgoing tracks, leading to separate terminals in the PCB. Therefore, the board has 4 terminals, two for the current injection path and the other two for voltage measurement. The only resistance contribution that cannot be avoided in this configuration is the one from the connection between the PCB pads and the sample electrodes. This is why achieving a sample integration with low DC resistance is crucial, as mentioned previously. To apply an external magnetic field through the sample thickness, a custom magnetic circuit was designed. It has a horizontal E-shaped core, with an airgap in the middle branch where the sample is positioned. One coil is wound around each of the other two branches, as can be seen in Figure 8. The generator was designed to achieve a 1 T field when a current of 3 A is supplied to the coils, which are connected in series.

Figure 8: Custom magnetic field generator with a test sample placed inside the airgap.

4.4. Printed Circuit Board Design

To be able to perform the electrical measurements, a custom PCB that meets the previously mentioned requirements was drawn using KiCad, an open-source PCB design suite [13]. The PCB was designed to have larger pads to allow for several wires if wire bonding is used, with each pad having two separate terminals, and a floating copper plane on the backside to help with thermal management of the sample. The drawing of the PCB is shown in Figure 9. The frontside copper is shown in red, and the two pads with two terminals each can be identified. The InSb sample is placed on a 10 mm x 10 mm exposed metal which also contains several vias for connection with the backside copper plane, in blue.

Figure 9: PCB design as drawn in KiCad suite. As a double-layer PCB, the top copper is shown in red and the bottom copper in blue.

A banana-type connector was soldered to each terminal, to match the terminals in the source meter. A test sample placed on the exposed metal and with electrical contact via wire bonding with Au wires can be seen in Figure 10. Two crater-like defects can be seen in the upper section of the rightmost electrode, due to higher power required for the bonding of thicker Aluminium wires.

Figure 10: Sample used for wire bonding test. Several Au wires of 25 μm diameter were used to make electrical connection between sample electrodes and PCB pads.

Banana sockets are also soldered to the PCB for connection with the sourcemeter, as can be seen in Figure 11. Voltage readings at zero field from the generator and at 1 T magnetic field are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13, respectively, while the sourcemeter supplies 10 mA to the MR element.

Figure 11: Top view of PCB after sample integration and soldering of banana sockets.

Figure 12: Sourcemeter supplying 10 mA fixed current and measuring voltage with independent terminals. Value of 0.79 mV at zero field.

Figure 13: Measured voltage increases to 10.06 mV at 1 T field, obtained from the custom field generator.

The sample presents a MR ratio above 1170 %. As mentioned earlier in the text, this final value is strongly dependent on sample geometry and its integration onto the PCB.

5. Conclusions

The report presented how magnetoresistive samples made of InSb are modelled, designed, fabricated and tested for current limiting applications. An analytical model was developed, and its limitations are better understood with support from FEM simulations. Two types of sample design were presented, and the planar design was chosen to proceed with. The fabrication steps followed in the cleanroom infrastructure available at Silicon Austria Labs have been underlined. Integration on PCBs was also discussed, with attention to the DC resistance contribution that comes with it. Issues related to thermal management were presented, and alternatives to mitigate the hindering impact of heat were investigated. The use of thermally conductive and electrical insulators to attach the sample to an exposed pad in the PCB was defined. The measurement setup consists of a commercial sourcemeter with 4-terminal configuration and a custom-made magnetic field generator.

The work here sets the foundations for the full development cycle of MR-based current limiters, with focus on the use of InSb as the high mobility material. The work will continue on the fabrication, integration and test of more samples tailored to the specific requirements obtained in the NOVETROL project, followed by system integration and validation of the passive and self-regulating current limiter solution.

References

- [1] S. A. Solin *et al*, Science 289, 1530 (2000), <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.289.5484.1530>
- [2] T. D. Pomar *et al*, Applied Materials Today, 38 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2024.102219>
- [3] J. Sun and J. Kosel, Apple. Phys. Lett., 100 (2012), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.4726431>
- [4] Ultra-high Sensitivity (InSb) Hall element from Asahi Kasei Microdevices, <https://www.akm.com/global/en/products/hall-sensor/hall-element/in-sb-ultra-high-sensitivity/>, accessed on 05.01.2026
- [5] Infineon GaN HEMTs <https://www.infineon.com/products/power/gallium-nitride/gallium-nitride-transistor>, accessed on 29.12.2025
- [6] HW101A Ultra High Sensitivity Hall Element, Asahi Kasei, <https://www.akm.com/global/en/products/hall-sensor/hall-element/in-sb-ultra-high-sensitivity/hw101a/>, accessed on 27.01.2026
- [7] O. M. Corbino, Nuovo Cim 1, 397–420 (1911). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02958241>
- [8] D. L. Rode, Phys. Rev. B, vol. 3, pp.3287-3299, 1971, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.3.3287>
- [9] M. Oswaldowski, and M. Zimpel, J. Phys. Chem. Solids, vol. 49, 1988, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697\(88\)90173-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697(88)90173-4)
- [10] Klayout, <https://www.klayout.de/>, accessed on 27.01.2026
- [11] Thermally conductive insulators, MTC, <https://www.mtc.de/en/tcp-products/thermally-conductive-insulators/thermally-conductive-insulators>, accessed on 07.01.2025
- [12] Ultra Temperature Epoxies, Cotronics Corp, https://www.cotronics.com/vo/cotr/ea_ultratemp.htm, accessed on 27.01.2026
- [13] KiCad, <https://www.kicad.org/>, accessed on 27.01.2026